

Calorimetric Study of Cadmium(II) and Lead(II) Complexes with Thiourea

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Precise calorimetric measurements of the Cd^{II}-thiourea and Pb^{II}-thiourea systems in 1 M NaClO₄ solution were made using a thermistor as the temperature measuring device in the system, and the values of the stepwise and overall changes in ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° accompanying the complex formation reactions were evaluated. Values of the overall enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) changes for the mono-, bis-, tris- and tetrakis-coordinated species are for Cd^{II} ion -10.75 and -7.7, -34.04 and -63.5, -20.81 and -17.8, -43.35 and -66.5, respectively; while for Pb^{II} ion -12.25 and -28.4, -19.16 and -57.4, -10.61 and -19.4, -39.80 and -84.8, respectively at 30° with $\mu = 1.0$.

In an earlier communication¹ we reported the results of polarographic study of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} complexes with thiourea. Application of De Ford and Hume's method showed the existence of 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 species in the thiourea concentration range 0.01–1 M. This paper presents the results of the calorimetric measurements of the heats of formation of these complexes. In addition, the free energy changes (ΔG°), enthalpy changes (ΔH°) and entropy changes (ΔS°) accompanying the complex forming reactions have been evaluated and compared with those derived earlier¹ from temperature dependence data.

Experimental

Calorimetric determination of heats of reaction was carried out for the Cd^{II}-thiourea and Pb^{II}-thiourea systems at 30° (± 0.02) and at the same ionic strength ($\mu = 1.0$) as used in the determination of formation constants by the polarographic method¹. As the complexes formed in the systems were weak and the reactions slightly exothermic, a much higher metal ion concentration was used in order to obtain heat changes which could be measured with sufficient accuracy. The equilibrium free ligand concentration, [L], values were calculated by carrying out a series of successive approximations using Bjerrum's² formation, \bar{n} , defined by the expressions

$$\bar{n} = \frac{\beta_1[L] + 2\beta_2[L]^2 + \dots + n\beta_n[L]^n}{1 + \beta_1[L] + \beta_2[L]^2 + \dots + \beta_n[L]^n} \quad (1)$$

$$= \frac{C_L - [L]}{C_M} \quad (2)$$

The calorimeter used in the present measurements was similar to that described by Sheomaker and Garland³ in its main features and was kept in a closed room at ambient temperature 29.5–30.5° with variation less than 0.2°. Stantal F-15 thermistor was used having 74410 Ω at 30.00° and a temperature coefficient of resistance $\sim 4\%$ per degree at this temperature. A Wheatstone bridge circuit using a L. N., E galvanometer with sensitivity 0.003 $\mu\text{A mm}^{-1}$ and a critical damping resistance of 495 Ω as null point detector, was used for measuring the resistance of the thermistor. A change in the resistance of the thermistor by 1 Ω corresponded to $\sim 0.00036^\circ$ and produced a galvanometer deflection of about 0.3 mm which was easily detectable. The relationship⁴

$$T_1 - T_2 = -K \log R_1/R_2 \quad (3)$$

where R_1 and R_2 are the resistances of the thermistor at temperatures T_1 and T_2 , respectively (measured with an accurate Beckman thermometer, Siebert Khün, Germany), and K is a constant valid only for a small temperature range, was obeyed fairly accurately by the thermistor. The average value of K of 20 determinations and extending over a period of 7 days for the temperature range 29.5–30.5°, was 59.485.

Heat equivalent of the calorimeter system was determined by measuring the temperature rise produced by the dissipation of a known quantity of electrical energy. The time measurements were made with a Stop Watch (0.1 sec, AOTT Kempton, D. R. G. M.). The energy input was determined by measuring the potential drop across a 0.1 Ω standard resistor with a current rating of 13 A (Pye Cat. No.

24522) with a K_a -potentiometer and a Tinsley 4500-A lamp and scale galvanometer having a sensitivity of $0.007 \mu\text{A mm}^{-1}$. The error limits were ± 0.2 sec for time measurement and ± 0.03 mV for i value.

Heat of reaction: Solutions for calorimetric experiments were prepared using the same reagents and the same procedures as reported earlier¹.

For each experiment 375 ml of solution of $\sim 1 M$ in NaClO_4 , $0.001 M$ in HClO_4 and containing varying amounts of thiourea were pipetted into a dry Dewar flask and 25 ml of metal perchlorate solution were pipetted into a plugged mixing pipette. After making necessary connections for the heater, the thermistor leads and the compressed nitrogen source to the mixing pipette, inside Dewar vessel, the chamber was closed and the stirrer was allowed to run. The temperature of the solution in the Dewar was adjusted to $30 \pm 0.05^\circ$ by switching on the calorimeter heater. The stop watch was started after a steady state was attained and the resistance of the thermistor recorded every 50 sec for a period of 10 min. The content of the mixing pipette were then blown off by passing compressed nitrogen gas, presaturated with $1 M$ NaClO_4 vapour at 30° , through the pipette and the gas pressure was released as soon as the gas started bubbling through the Dewar solution as shown by sudden jerk in the flow manometer levels. Measurements of the resistance against temperature were again carried out every 50 sec for a period of 10 min. The heater was then switched on, and the current allowed to flow through the heater exactly for 300 sec and the potential drop across the standard 0.1Ω resistance was noted every 50 sec. After switching off the heater, the content of the pipette were blown out as before and the thermistor resistance recorded every 50 sec for a period of about 10 min.

The resistance of the thermistor before and after mixing the solutions was obtained from the extrapolation of the plots of resistance vs time, to the time of mixing. Since the mixing of the solutions took place in less than 10 sec, no radiation correction was necessary for the values obtained by extrapolation. The resistance of the thermistor before and after heating the solution was obtained from the extrapolation of the time-resistance plots to the middle of the heating period, and the values obtained were corrected for the radiation loss.

Results and Discussion

Cadmium^{II} perchlorate-thiourea system: The results of the heat of mixing of cadmium^{II} perchlorate solution with thiourea solutions of concentrations 0.1 - $1 M$ are tabulated in Table 1. The final temperature (extrapolated value) after mixing the solutions was corrected for the endothermic heat of dilution of $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and of NaClO_4 solutions.

The equilibrium concentrations of the uncomplexed thiourea, $[L]$, in the experimental solutions

TABLE 1—HEAT OF MIXING OF SOLUTION OF $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ ($0.02163 M$) WITH SOLUTIONS OF THIOUREA AT 30° ($\mu=1.0$)

Thiourea M	Heat liberated J	Heat of reaction kJ mol^{-1}	Average heat of reaction ΔH° kJ mol^{-1}
0.1	166.00	16.85	16.89
	166.93	16.94	
0.2	268.12	27.21	27.15
	266.91	27.09	
0.3	328.79	33.37	33.42
	329.63	33.46	
0.4	363.88	36.98	36.99
	365.13	37.06	
0.5	380.71	38.64	38.63
	380.58	38.63	
0.6	394.27	40.02	40.10
	395.95	40.19	
0.7	402.52	40.85	40.94
	404.24	41.03	
0.8	409.89	41.60	41.52
	408.88	41.45	
0.9	410.89	41.70	41.75
	411.81	41.80	
1.0	414.03	42.02	42.12
	415.83	42.21	

were calculated by four successive approximations by the procedure outlined before³ (eqns. 1 and 2) and the α_n values were calculated from equation (4) using polarographic values¹ of formation constants, β_n obtained at 30°

$$\alpha_n = \frac{\beta_n [L]^n}{1 + \beta_1 [L] + \beta_2 [L]^2 + \dots + \beta_n [L]^n} \quad (4)$$

From the experimentally measured ΔH° values and the calculated α_n values, a set of 10 simultaneous equations were obtained, from which by least-squares procedure a set of four normal simultaneous equations of the following types were obtained

$$\Delta H_1^\circ \Sigma \alpha_1^2 + \Delta H_2^\circ \Sigma \alpha_1 \alpha_2 + \Delta H_3^\circ \Sigma \alpha_1 \alpha_3 + \Delta H_4^\circ \Sigma \alpha_1 \alpha_4 = \Delta H^\circ \alpha_1 \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta H_1^\circ \Sigma \alpha_1 \alpha_2 + \Delta H_2^\circ \Sigma \alpha_2^2 + \Delta H_3^\circ \Sigma \alpha_2 \alpha_3 + \Delta H_4^\circ \Sigma \alpha_2 \alpha_4 = \Delta H^\circ \alpha_2 \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta H_1^\circ \Sigma \alpha_1 \alpha_3 + \Delta H_2^\circ \Sigma \alpha_2 \alpha_3 + \Delta H_3^\circ \Sigma \alpha_3^2 + \Delta H_4^\circ \Sigma \alpha_3 \alpha_4 = \Delta H^\circ \alpha_3 \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta H_1^\circ \Sigma \alpha_1 \alpha_4 + \Delta H_2^\circ \Sigma \alpha_2 \alpha_4 + \Delta H_3^\circ \Sigma \alpha_3 \alpha_4 + \Delta H_4^\circ \Sigma \alpha_4^2 = \Delta H^\circ \alpha_4 \quad (8)$$

the solution of which gave the values of ΔH_1° , ΔH_2° , ΔH_3° and ΔH_4° . The overall entropy changes, ΔS_n° for the various complex formation reactions were calculated from ΔH_n° values using the expression,

$$\Delta S_n^\circ = \frac{H_n^\circ + RT \ln \beta_n}{T} \quad (9)$$

Lead^{II} perchlorate-thiourea system: The results of heat of mixing of solutions of lead perchlorate and thiourea are tabulated in Table 2. As $\text{Pb}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4$ thiourea was found to be sparingly soluble in solutions containing excess of thiourea, smaller concentrations of lead perchlorate was used in experiments with higher concentration of thiourea.

TABLE 2—HEAT OF MIXING OF SOLUTION OF Pb(ClO₄)₂ WITH SOLUTION OF THIOUREA AT 30° (μ=1.0)

Thiourea M	Pb(ClO ₄) ₂ mM	Heat liberated J	Heat of reaction kJ mol ⁻¹	Average heat of reaction ΔH° kJ mol ⁻¹
0.2	20.71	82.98	10.02	9.96
		82.10	9.91	
0.3	20.71	150.22	18.14	18.23
		151.94	18.32	
0.4	20.71	204.40	24.79	24.91
		205.49	25.04	
10.35	10.35	127.15	30.71	30.59
		126.19	30.47	
0.6	10.35	140.22	33.85	33.92
		140.76	33.99	
0.7	5.19	72.81	35.15	35.02
		72.26	34.90	
0.8	5.19	74.15	35.81	35.73
		73.73	35.65	
0.9	5.19	74.40	35.94	36.04
		74.82	36.14	
1.0	5.19	77.16	37.25	37.30
		76.79	37.35	

For Cd^{II}-thiourea system, a comparison of the ΔH° values for the various complex formation reactions obtained by the present calorimetric method and from the temperature dependence data of the polarographic measurements¹, as given in Table 3, shows that there is a reasonably good agreement between the two sets of values, and the same may be seen in the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 4 complex species in the Pb^{II}-thiourea system, in spite of small values of the stability constants and small temperature coefficients of the complexes in the latter system.

In both systems the observed trend $K_n > K_{n+1}$ is what is usually observed in most systems due to electrostatic and statistical effects² along with dative π-bonding⁵ from metal to ligand⁶, though reversal⁶⁻⁸ of this general order has been observed in the higher complexes.

From the present data it is clear that Cd^{II} forms stronger complex than Pb^{II} with thiourea. This can be explained through the π-interaction^{5,9} in terms of M→L, π bond in addition to M←L, σ bond, since Cd^{II} has d¹⁰ configuration and the vacant dπ orbitals are available on the sulphur atom for the back-coordination. Furthermore, the formation of dπ-dπ bond in addition to σ bond would tend to neutralize the formal charges set up on the ligand and the metal by the formation of the σ bond, thus effecting a simultaneous strengthening of the latter. Besides, Cd^{II} ion with a higher electron affinity and smaller ionic radius¹⁰ than Pb^{II} ion is also expected to form a stronger σ bond than the latter and formation of either bond would favour development of the other.

The greater electron transfer from further thiourea molecules would make the metal orbital larger thus resulting in larger overlap. With Cd^{II} ion where 3d orbitals have shorter lobes, such interactions would be smaller. The higher values of K₃ and K₄ for the Pb^{II}-thiourea system and high values of K₄ in both these systems are, therefore, expected in spite of a greater tendency of Cd^{II} ion for π-interaction.

The unfavourable entropy values (Table 3) may be neither due to a reduction in the number of ions in the system nor to the weakening of the electrical charge by charge neutralization, with uncharged, feebly hydrated, unidentate ligand like thiourea, involving bivalent metal ions having a great ordering effect on the solvent. The complexation is, therefore, favoured by negative enthalpy change which further supports the M-S π-interaction. The small exothermic values suggest that the bonds formed are relatively weaker, and is the consequence of the reduction of the repulsive forces between neighbouring donor atoms in the complex formed with thiourea. The abrupt occurrence of the reversal in the contribution of these terms for the formation of the tricoordinated complex species may possibly

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC CONSTANTS OF CADMIUM(II)-THIOUREA AND LEAD(II)-THIOUREA COMPLEXES AT 30° (μ=1.0)

System	Formation constants		ΔH°† kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS°(±0.05)† J deg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔH°§ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS°(±0.05)§ J deg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	log K _n /K _{n+1}
	Over-all* (β _n)	Stepwise (K)					
A	β ₁ =28	K ₁ =28	-11.97	-11.8	-10.75	-7.7	-
A	β ₂ =350	-	-30.61	-52.2	-34.04	-68.5	-
A	β ₃ =450	-	-23.89	-28.0	-20.81	-17.8	-
A	β ₄ =9850	-	-43.64	-67.4	-43.34	-66.5	-
A	-	K ₂ =12.5	-18.63	-40.4	-23.29	-55.8	+0.35
A	-	K ₃ =1.29	+6.71	+24.2	+13.23	+45.7	+0.99
A	-	K ₄ =21.89	-19.74	-39.5	-22.53	-48.7	-1.23
B	β ₁ =4.25	K ₁ =4.25	-10.11	-21.3	-12.25	-28.4	-
B	β ₂ =2.00	-	-7.98	-20.6	-19.16	-57.4	-
B	β ₃ =6.50	-	-17.56	-42.3	-10.61	-19.4	-
B	β ₄ =265.00	-	-36.72	-74.7	-39.80	-84.8	-
B	-	K ₂ =0.47	+2.13	+0.8	-6.91	-29.0	+0.96
B	-	K ₃ =3.25	-9.58	-21.8	+8.55	+38.0	-0.84
B	-	K ₄ =40.77	-19.16	-32.3	-29.19	-65.5	-1.10

A : Cadmium(II)-thiourea, B : Lead(II)-thiourea,

* Polarographic data at 30°; † temperature dependence data Ref. 1; § polarographic data.

be due to some decrease in coordination number of the central ion followed by a change in the stereochemistry showing a sudden increase of the disruption of hydration sphere surrounding the cation, occurring at this step of complexation. The necessity for rearrangement of the coordination sphere in the uptake of the third thiourea molecule is thus reflected in the positive entropy change. Possibility of coexistence in solution of complexes of different coordination stereochemistry have been noted in thiourea and substituted thiourea complexes^{8,11}.

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References

1. S. N. BANERJEE and C. E. S. VAZ, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 387.
2. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Hæsse and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941, p. 40.
3. D. P. SHROMAKER and C. W. GARLAND, "Experiments in Physical Chemistry", McGraw Hill, New York, 1962, p. 119.
4. H. A. SKINNER (Ed), "Experimental Thermochemistry", Interscience, 1962, Vol. II, p. 169.
5. "Modern Coordination Chemistry", ed. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINS, Interscience, New York, 1960, p. 37.
6. D. D. DE FORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5321.
7. H. IRVING, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 4056.
8. K. SWAMINATHAN and H. IRVING, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 171.
9. R. S. NYHOLM, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 273.
10. R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 121.
11. S. L. HOLT and R. L. GARLIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 3017.